

Born Again Atonement
John 3:1-21
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John 3:1 Now there was a man of the Pharisees, named “Nicodemus, a ^bruler of the Jews; ² this man came to Jesus by night and said to Him, ““Rabbi, we know that You have come from God ^aas a teacher; for no one can do these ^{1b}signs that You do unless ‘God is with him.’” ³ Jesus answered and said to him, “Truly, truly, I say to you, unless one ^ais born ¹again he cannot see ^bthe kingdom of God.”

John 3:4 Nicodemus ^{*}said to Him, “How can a man be born when he is old? He cannot enter a second time into his mother’s womb and be born, can he?” ⁵ Jesus answered, “Truly, truly, I say to you, unless one is born of ^awater and the Spirit he cannot enter into ^bthe kingdom of God. ⁶ ““That which is born of the flesh is flesh, and that which is born of the Spirit is spirit. ⁷ “Do not be amazed that I said to you, ‘You must be born ¹again.’” ⁸ ““The wind blows where it wishes and you hear the sound of it, but do not know where it comes from and where it is going; so is everyone who is born of the Spirit.”

John 3:9 Nicodemus said to Him, “How can these things be?” ¹⁰ Jesus answered and said to him, “Are you ^athe teacher of Israel and do not understand these things? ¹¹ “Truly, truly, I say to you, ^awe speak of what we know and ^btestify of what we have seen, and ^byou do not accept our testimony. ¹² “If I told you earthly things and you do not believe, how will you believe if I tell you heavenly things? ¹³ ““No one has ascended into heaven, but ^bHe who descended from heaven: ‘the Son of Man. ¹⁴ “As ^aMoses lifted up the serpent in the wilderness, even so must ^bthe Son of Man ^bbe lifted up; ¹⁵ so that whoever ¹believes will ^ain Him have eternal life.

John 3:16 “For God so ^aloved the world, that He ^bgave His ^{1c}only begotten Son, that whoever ^abelieves in Him shall not perish, but have eternal life. ¹⁷ “For God ^adid not send the Son into the world ^bto judge the world, but that the world might be saved through Him. ¹⁸ ““He who believes in Him is not judged; he who does not believe has been judged already, because he has not believed in the name of ^bthe ¹only begotten Son of God. ¹⁹ “This is the judgment, that ^athe Light has come into the world, and men loved the darkness rather than the Light, for ^btheir deeds were evil. ²⁰ ““For everyone who does evil hates the Light, and does not come to the Light for fear that his deeds will be exposed. ²¹ “But he who ^apractices the truth comes to the Light, so that his deeds may be manifested as having been wrought in God.”

During the time of the writing of John’s Gospel, we know that anti-Semitism was at a height for the church. Anything Jewish was being rejected. In addition, Paul’s original churches were trying to convert people from the worship of Mithras to the worship of Jesus. Throughout these centuries, the church had adopted culture and rituals from the people they wanted to convert to Christianity. In that view, can one look at being born again as meaning, in that day, changing your religious outlook from

Judaism or Mithras to Christianity? There is strong possibility and supportive evidence that the church used this concept in the conversion of many people. Jesus was saying whether we are Jewish or not, we need to understand that if we are following a religion that was man-made or had a strong human influence, the religion may not be a part of the kingdom of God. In order to enter the kingdom of God, one must be able to erase all past beliefs and behaviors and live and believe in the Son of God. Many Christians and Jews have lost their way from God and need a rebirth in faith and religion. Going under that premise, reborn today would mean looking at one's faith and practices to see if they are following the kingdom of God, nonviolent, and filled with love and grace.

Substitution theology, Jesus died for our sins, has been with the church for many centuries. Examining this passage offers a deeper meaning. Did Jesus die because of our sins? The violent world killed Him. However, the violent world was created by sins. Therefore, to say that our sins killed Jesus does work. His death and resurrection show us the path to eternal life for those who believe in Jesus. The belief of the soul remaining in Sheol has been proven wrong. Following Jesus in life means following Jesus in death, and that journey ends in Heaven.

I realize that this view is going to be considered radical. Jesus came to show us the way to Heaven that had been lost to Israel centuries earlier. The secret Law of God was revealed to Moses on Mount Sinai when he received the Torah. The secret to entering Heaven is to love God and to love neighbor. That is what it is all about. Now how do we accomplish this? That is the rub.

The simple answer is to follow the ways of Jesus. He demonstrated how to live a life following the ways of the LORD. Jesus came to fulfill the Torah and the prophets. If you follow the way Jesus acted and spoke, you will find that your words and actions are in accordance with the LORD. What is the result? You will obtain eternal life with Jesus and God.

This is not an easy life. But wait, then what does Jesus' death mean if one takes this atonement approach? Jesus died because he brought us the message. Jesus died because He believed in the message. How many people do you know who would give up their life for a belief? Jesus did. Prophets were killed throughout history because the established leaders did not like the message. Jesus wants us to follow the LORD's law first and the world second. Worldly kings and dictators do not want to hear this. Human leaders think that they come first. Throughout history, such leaders have used violence and death to ensure their continual power over the people. This is happening today in many nations around the world.

Jesus was put to death because He tells us that following worldly leaders first is idolatry. Following the LORD first is the way to Heaven. So many countries throughout history claimed to establish their laws following the Bible. Many started that way, but over time human intervention took over. In many countries, it is hard to place God first. As believers and followers of Jesus Christ, we must try as hard as possible to do this.

Jesus and the ways he demonstrated to us must come first. Everything else must become secondary. May you live a life that is pleasing to God by following the words

and actions of Jesus Christ. By doing so, you have become born again. Following Jesus' way will save you from a life of sin and will open the gates of Heaven.